

Abstract**Association of Anti-Chlamydial Antibodies with Spontaneous Miscarriage**

Agbogo E. O.^{1*}, Chama C.², Hassan O.T.¹, Achanya S. E.¹, Ugwu I.¹,

Author Affiliations

¹Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, Federal University of Health Sciences Teaching Hospital, Azare, Bauchi State, Nigeria

²Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University Teaching Hospital, Bauchi State, Nigeria

***Correspondence:** Emmanuel Agbogo.
Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology,
Federal University of Health Sciences
Teaching Hospital, Azare, Bauchi State
Nigeria. Email:
emmanuel.agbogo@fuhsa.edu.ng
Tel:+2348035392616

Background: Miscarriage is a common adverse pregnancy outcome with significant impact on the woman's health, her family and the community at large. Chlamydia trachomatis is the commonest Sexually Transmitted Infection worldwide and has been implicated in the aetiology of miscarriage. However, its role in spontaneous miscarriage is still unclear, as reports are conflicting. This study determined the association between Chlamydia trachomatis infection and spontaneous miscarriage.

Materials and Method: This case-control study was conducted at the Gynaecological Emergency/Clinic and Antenatal Clinic of the Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University Teaching Hospital, Bauchi. Eighty-five women with spontaneous miscarriage (case group) were compared with eighty-five women with on-going pregnancy beyond twenty-eight weeks

of gestation and no prior miscarriage (control group) matched for age and parity. Sera was obtained from both groups and tested for the presence of Chlamydia IgG antibodies using ELISA diagnostic techniques. The data obtained, including their socio-demographic characteristics, were recorded and analysed using IBM SPSS version 26.

Results: The overall sero-prevalence of Chlamydia trachomatis IgG among the participants in this study was 7.1%, while the prevalence for the case group was 10.6%, and that for the control group was 3.5%. This difference in sero-prevalence was not statistically significant. (p=0.132, OR=3.237, CI=0.845-12.407)

Conclusion: Demonstration of the association of chlamydia with miscarriage was not established in this study. Chlamydia trachomatis IgG was detected more in women with miscarriage than in those without miscarriage, suggesting an increased risk for miscarriage from exposure to the organism. The ELISA diagnostic technique alone may not be sufficient if screening of pregnant women is to be undertaken. A multicenter prospective cohort study employing a combination of PCR and ELISA may yield further clarity in the future.

Keywords: Chlamydia trachomatis, Miscarriage, IgG, ELISA.

Open Access article distribution in the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (CC by 4.0)

Copyright: The Author(s). 2025

ISSN: Print; 2992-555X Electronic: 3092-9865

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18902222>

Date Submitted: 20th November 2025

Date Accepted: 2nd March 2026

Date Published Online: 10th March 2026

Cite this article as: Agbogo E. O., Chama C., Hassan O.T., Achanya S. E., Ugwu I., Association of Anti-Chlamydial Antibodies with Spontaneous Miscarriage *The Scholar J Health Scie* 2026; S2-3